

The Effect of Workload and Work Stress on Employee Job Satisfaction on Lucky Plaza Batam Cellular Data Store

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to ascertain how work stress and workload affect employee satisfaction at the HP secular Lucky Plaza Batam store. Situated at Jl. Imam Bonjol, Lubuk Baja Kota, Lubuk Baja District, Batam City, Riau Islands, the HP secular Lucky Plaza Batam Store served as the research site for this study. Researchers use a quantitative population. Up to 50 employees of the HP Secular Lucky Plaza Batam Store work in this area. Research findings indicate that workload has an impact on job satisfaction among employees at the HP Secular Lucky Plaza Batam Store. Stress at work has an impact on job satisfaction at the HP secular Lucky Plaza Batam Store. Stress at work and workload at the same time affect Job Satisfaction at HP secular Lucky Plaza Batam Store.

INTRODUCTION

Employees are a key component of the organization's human resources for accomplishing its objectives. The contentment at work factor in an organization is very important. Workers with a high degree of job satisfaction will work diligently and innovatively or behave positively towards their work, and vice versa. When workers experience low levels of job satisfaction, workers work performance is low and will even behave negatively towards their work such as laziness, undiscipline at work, and others, of course, this will affect the goals of the organization.

Job satisfaction as a match between the expectations of an employee and the benefits he gets from his job. The capacity to effectively use human resources to manage mental, emotional, or response-related disorders is known as stress management. Employees who are happy with their jobs typically produce higher work results or performance even allowing for individual development initiatives for the betterment of the organization. Employees who are dissatisfied with their jobs tend to only complete workplace tasks at a minimum. The relationship between employee job satisfaction and performance. Workload overload is a big problem for all organizations. Some people experience pressure due to overwork; some may experience job dissatisfaction. It is imperative that the organization understands the needs of its employees and provides the best for its employees.

Situated on Jl. Imam Bonjol, Lubuk Baja City, Lubuk Baja District, Batam City, Riau Islands, the HP secular Lucky Plaza Batam store sells smartphones and processes Telkom's starter packs. Companies in this store need to take into account a number of factors, including job satisfaction, workload, and stress at work. It is necessary to take this factor into account once more to ensure that the work completed complies with the relevant company policies.

Job satisfaction can rise with a low workload while it can fall with a high workload. This is due to the fact that employees' capacity and ability do not match the tasks that need to be completed, which results in their inability to finish work. The workload that occurs based on observations shows that the quality of employee work is still not careful and meticulous so that errors arise in the implementation of duties. Punctuality of employees in carrying out tasks is still slow, thus incomplete or unfinished work will get additional work hours so that work can be completed. Many workers also express dissatisfaction with the state of the room, which is dark and closed off, making it difficult for air to circulate. Additionally, many workers believe that the work assigned does not correspond with the outcomes, that awards for exceptional workers are rarely given out, and that training is still not provided in a sufficient amount.

Tension that impacts a person's emotions, thoughts, and physical state is known as work stress. An inability to positively interact with one's surroundings, both the outside world and one's workplace, is typically the outcome of improperly managed stress. Stress at work that occurs in employees of HP Secular Lucky Plaza Batam Store is that many employees complain that the salaries and bonuses paid are not in accordance with the results of the work

that employees have done. In addition, incentives are often paid late, as promised incentives will be paid on every 5th of the following month, but in reality, incentives are received in the middle of the following month. The many negligence's of management in paying attention to the compensation given, make employees become unfocused and lose the enthusiasm to work optimally, thus making employees lazy.

Job A person's level of satisfaction is their emotional state about something he does. If someone feels satisfied with what he has done, then it will usually indirectly affect his career. This is because someone who is satisfied at work will be serious about working, so that his performance increases and in the end his career will increase. So, job satisfaction will affect career either directly or indirectly through other variables such as performance (intervening According to observations, there is still a significant lack of job satisfaction among employees of the HP secular Lucky Plaza Batam Store. A number of employees have voiced grievances regarding the number of jobs they perform for meagre pay, which contributes to their discontent. Employees are rarely promoted for promotion, so employees working in the same field of duty for a long time will easily make employees feel bored. Monotonous work routines every day, at one time will definitely reach the point of saturation, which can result in employees not being able to maximally release their abilities for the progress of the company.

Work stress appears in additional mental states like stress, worry, and anger. It is obvious that stress and dissatisfaction will rise when people are assigned to jobs with conflicting demands or where there is uncertainty regarding the responsibilities, authorities, and duties of the job bearer. High work stress can affect employee disruption in making a high-risk decision for patients being treated. When work stress experienced by high employees can have an impact on workers' emotional and physical health and can cause less than optimal for a nurse at work and can make employees wrong in doing their jobs. Meanwhile, if employee work stress is low, it can have a good impact on the performance of an employee and can make employees optimal in working to serve the community as a whole in the hospital.

The author's pre-survey, which involved distributing 25 questionnaires about various aspects of employee job satisfaction at the HP secular Lucky Plaza Batam Store, yielded the following results:

Table 1. Pre-Survey Results of Job Satisfaction Variables of HP secular Lucky Store Employees Plaza Batam

No	Indicator	Statement	Answer	
			Agree	Disagree
1	Work	The work I do is beyond my ability	17 (70%)	8 (30%)
2	Wages	The wages given are not in accordance with the performance I do	20 (85%)	5 (15%)
3	Promotion	The company provides promotions for every employee who has good performance	16 (65%)	9 (35%)
4	Co workers	My communication with colleagues is not good	11 (40%)	14 (60%)

Source: Primary Data 2023

It can be seen in table 1 that 20 employees of HP secular Lucky Plaza Batam Store were respondents to the pre-survey conducted by the author, as many as 70% said they agreed with the work I did beyond my ability and 30% said they disagreed. On the wage variable, 85% of respondents agreed that the wages given were not in accordance with the performance I did, while 15% of respondents disagreed. In the promotion variable, 65% of respondents agreed that the company provides a promotion for every employee who has good performance while 35% said they disagreed, while in the co-worker variable 40% of respondents agreed that my communication with colleagues was not good while 69% of respondents disagreed.

High workload will cause high work stress, based on observations made by many employees who feel stressed because of their work where each employee is asked to achieve targets exceeding the set targets in a little time, this makes employees feel stressed with the pressure they receive. This is in accordance Salapiah (2021) found in his earlier study, *The Effect of Workload and Work Stress on Employee Job Satisfaction at PT. Banua Petra Prima Kota Banjarmasin*, that stress at work prevents employees from feeling satisfied with their jobs.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Library Survey

Workload (X1)

The product of the volume of work and the standard time is the workload, or the amount of work that an individual or organizational unit must perform. Utilizing the following metrics: (1) Working Conditions; (2) Utilization of Working Time; and (3) Achievable Goals As of 2017 Koesomowidjojo.

Work Stress (x2)

Work stress is a conducive tension caused by pressure in individuals that create imbalances in the body and mind that impact a person's emotions, mental processes, and state of readiness for work. Task demands, role demands, interpersonal demands, and organizational leadership's provision of management style to the organization are the following indicators (Afandi, 2018).

Job Satisfaction (Y)

When one evaluates one's work as a means of appreciating the accomplishment of one of the key values of the organization, one can determine whether or not the workforce has a positive attitude toward their work job. With the following indicators, (1) Employment, (2) Wages, (3) Promotions, (4) Co-workers (Afandi, 2018).

Frame of Thought

Sumber: Koesomowidjojo (2017), Afandi (2018)

Figure 1. Framework of Thought

Research Hypothesis

A hypothesis is a tentative solution to a problem statement for a study. when the formulation of the problem takes the shape of a question. It is referred to as temporary because the solutions provided are merely predicated on pertinent theories and have not yet been verified by empirical facts gathered through data collection. (Sugiyono, 2017).

H1: There is a suspicion that workload influences the Job Satisfaction of employees of HP secular Lucky Plaza Batam Store.

H2: Workplace stress may have a partial impact on employees' job satisfaction HP secular Lucky Plaza Batam Store employees.

H3: It is suspected that workload and work stress have a simultaneous impact on employees' job satisfaction HP secular Lucky Plaza Batam Store

METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this study is to ascertain how work stress and workload affect the job satisfaction of HP secular Lucky Plaza Batam Store employees. Employees of the HP secular Lucky Plaza Batam Store, which is situated on Jl. Imam Bonjol in Lubuk Baja Kota, Kec. Lubuk Baja, Batam City, Riau Islands, were the subjects of this study. A population is a broad category made up of things or people with specific attributes chosen by researchers to be investigated and conclusions made from (Sugiyono, 2017). The people who utilized by the author is quantitative. Where the population is employees of HP secular Lucky Plaza Batam Store as many as 50 people. The sample selection method uses Saturated Sampling: This type of sampling involves using every member of the population as a sample. All fifty (50) employees of the Lucky Plaza Batam Mobile Phone Store made up the research sample for this study. This study's method for gathering data includes interviews, documentation, and questionnaires methods. The scores of the respondents are summed, so that this number is the total score which is then processed using SPSS version 26.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Multiple Linear Regression

Table 2. Multiple Linear Regression

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	32,636	5,258		6,208	0,000
	Workload	0,296	0,093	0,448	3,194	0,003
	Work stress	0,268	0,124	0,303	2,158	0,038
a. Dependent Variable: Job satisfaction						

Source: Processed Researcher, 2023

The values in the output above are then entered into the multiple the following regression equation:

$$Y = 32,636 + 0,296X1 + 0,268X2 + e$$

The values in the preceding equation are as follows:

1. The value of Constant (a) of 32.636 means that workload and work streif it is 0 (zero) then job satisfaction is 32.636.
2. The variable value of workload value of 0.296 can be interpreted that every increase in workload by 1 will affect the value of job satisfaction by 0.296 assuming the value of work stress is constant.

- The work stress variable value of 0.268 indicates that, under the assumption that the workload is constant, every increase in work stress of 1 will result in an increase in the job satisfaction value of 0.268.

Partial Test (t Test)

Table 3. Test t

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	32,639	5,258		6,208	0,000
	Workload	0,296	0,093	0,448	3,194	0,003
	Work stress	0,268	0,1214	0,303	2,158	0,038
a. Dependent Variable: Job satisfaction						

Source: Processed Researcher, 2023

It is possible to conclude that all independent variables have a significant impact on the dependent variable because the hypothesis test results in the above table indicate that all independent variables, including workload and work stress, have a significance of < 0.05 . namely job satisfaction, with the following explanation:

- The effect of workload on job satisfaction: The workload variable had a computed t value of $3.194 > 1.687$ t table with a significant level of $0.003 < 0.05$ based on the t test results. This explains why job satisfaction is significantly and positively impacted by the workload variable in part. Therefore, the first hypothesis (H1) can be considered accepted.
- The effect of job stress on job satisfaction: The work stress variable had a computed t value of $2.158 > 1.687$ t table with a significant level of $0.038 < 0.05$ based on the t test results. This explains why job satisfaction is significantly and positively impacted by the work stress variable. Therefore, it follows that the second hypothesis (H2) is true.

Simulate Test (F Test)

Table 4. Test F

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	380,403	2	190,201	12,971	,000 ^b
	Residual	542,572	37	14,664		
	Total	922,975	39			
a. Dependent Variable: Job satisfaction						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Workload, Work stress						

Source: Researcher's Process, 2023

Determined by taking the F test results from the table above and computing the F value of 12.971 was obtained with a significant value of 0.015 ($0.000 < 0.05$), while the F table at the price level of 5% ($\alpha = 0.05$) was 4.11. This means $F_{count} > F_{table}$ ($12.971 > 4.11$). The calculation shows that the variables workload and work stress jointly significantly impact job satisfaction, or in other words the fourth hypothesis (H3) is accepted.

Test Coefficient of Determination (R2)

Table 5. Coefficient of Determination

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	DurbinWatson
1	0.842	0.612	0.580	3.82938	2.364
a. Predictors: (Constant), Workload, Work stress					
b. Dependent Variable: Job satisfaction					

Source: Researcher's Process, 2023

Workload (X1) and work stress (X2) account for 58.0% of the job satisfaction variable (Y), according to the coefficient of determination (R2) test results displayed in the above table. That figure is 0.580. However, other factors not included in this study can account for the remaining 42.0%.

1. The Effect of Workload on Job Satisfaction of HP secular Lucky Store Employees Plaza Batam

The hypothesis test results provide an explanation for the workload variable's partial, significant, and positive impact on job satisfaction. An excessive workload can have a negative impact on an employee's job satisfaction because it can lead to physical and mental exhaustion as well as emotional reactions like headaches, indigestion, and irritability. While on a workload that is too little will cause boredom and monotony.

In reference to the findings of Chirrya Citra Ramadhan's research (2017), it can be observed that work stress (X1) and workload (X2) have a positive and

significant influence on job satisfaction (Y). These two factors can contribute to the formation of Job Satisfaction (Y). This suggests that there is a real, unidirectional relationship between free variability (work stress and workload) and related variables (Job Satisfaction) that occurs concurrently. Put another way, if work stress (X1) and workload (X2) are increased, they can also raise Job Satisfaction (Y).

Workload is needed to be able to help individuals improve the way employees work. The product of the volume of work and the standard time is the work load, or the amount of work that an individual or organizational unit must perform. A sense of boredom will arise if an employee's abilities exceed the demands of the work. On the other hand, there will be greater weariness if employees' abilities fall short of what is required of them. Three conditions apply to the workload that is charged to employees: the workload that is in compliance with standards; the workload that is excessive (overcapacity); and the workload that is insufficient (under capacity). Workload is a key factor that influences feelings and creates feelings of instability towards employees. However, in the factors of workload and job satisfaction in employees, it can be felt that although the workload is very high, the job satisfaction obtained is also balanced with what they feel (Hermingsih & Purwanti, 2020).

2. The Effect of Work Stress on Job Satisfaction of HP secular Lucky Store Employees Plaza Batam

The hypothesis test results provide an explanation for the positive and significant impact of the partial work stress variable on job satisfaction. Workplace stress is the pressure that workers feel to perform their jobs well. The manifestations of this work-related stress include erratic emotions, uneasiness, a preference for solitude, trouble falling asleep, heavy smoking, difficulty relaxing, anxiety, tension, and nervousness, elevated blood pressure, and digestive issues. Stress can lead to tense situations that impact a person's mood, cognitive function, and physical health, ultimately influencing how satisfied an employee is with their work.

Referring In line with the findings of Cahyani's study, Yesia Lien (2021) demonstrates that work-related stress positively and significantly affects Ibnu Sina Islamic Hospital Pekanbaru employees' job satisfaction. Stress at work is an employee's physical and/or psychological response to something they feel is dangerous or burdensome. Workplace stress is a state of tension that impairs an employee's five emotions, cognitive processes, and general well-being in addition to causing a physical and psychological imbalance. When stress is untreated, it can have a negative effect on one's health since it causes an individual to suppress their inner selves and themselves to an extent that is beyond their capacity. Several of these definitions of work-related stress led to the conclusion that the definition of work stress is a stressful situation or circumstance, both physically and psychologically, which can affect the condition of an employee (Tinambunan et al., 2022).

3. The Effect of Work Load and Stress on HP Store Employee Job Satisfaction Lucky Plaza Batam Cellular

Based on study findings, the Lucky Plaza Batam Cellular HP Store employees' job satisfaction is partially and simultaneously impacted by their workload and work stress. If workers experience the expected level of job satisfaction while working, they will feel at ease. The perception of whether or not an employee enjoys their work, as well as their positive behaviour toward it and everything they encounter at work, are indicators of their job satisfaction. If a job task's workload causes issues, like the need to complete tasks quickly, produce something so that the workload can make employees less comfortable at work.

In addition to the workload that is employee pressure, Workplace stress is a state of tension that leads to physical and psychological imbalances. These imbalances impact an employee's emotions, cognitive functions, and overall health. Obviously, they also have an impact on whether or not an employee is satisfied with their job at a company. A workload is the result of taking on too many tasks or not enough time to finish them.

Workload is one of the most complained about stress-causing factors and the primary motivator for workers in a company. High workloads are a common issue in the workplace. In addition, when combined with the stress of working on projects that depress and anxious workers, Saleh (2018). Every task must be finished as soon as possible, precisely, and carefully due to the workload. And occasionally, in specific situations, the deadline can actually increase motivation and produce high performance.

Work stress is an adaptive response that is constrained by psychological processes and individual differences. It is the result of any activity (environment), circumstance, or outside event that places an excessive amount of psychological or physical demands on an individual while they are in that particular location. According to Nurmalasari (2015), the term "eustress" refers to positive stress, whereas "tress" denotes excessive and detrimental stress. In principle, human resources, namely employees, are the exclusive assets that establish the organization. Ambitious organizations possess advanced facilities and infrastructure, but achieving objectives is likely to be challenging in the absence of strong human resources. Human resources are the fundamental assets of an organization that enable it to carry out tasks in the pursuit of its objectives. They are strengths that stem from human potential within the organization.

Employees need to have job satisfaction in a company where they work. According to Afandi (2018), job satisfaction is defined as an employee's positive attitude toward their work, including their feelings and behaviours, as well as their assessment of their job as a sign of appreciation for reaching one of the key work-related values. A person's emotional state toward their work, whether it be pleasant or unpleasant, is a reflection of their job satisfaction.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

These inferences can be made in light of the findings of the research that has been done.

- a. The workload at the HP secular Lucky Plaza Batam Store has an impact on workers' job satisfaction.
- b. Workplace stress has an impact on employees' job satisfaction at the HP secular Lucky Plaza Batam Store.
- c. Workload and work-related stress both have an impact on the job satisfaction of HP secular Lucky Plaza Batam Store employees.

The researcher offers the following recommendations in light of the findings of the investigation.

- a. In order to improve employee satisfaction at work, it is expected that businesses practice human resource management by paying attention to employee workload and work stress.
- b. It is expected that companies can prioritize employee job satisfaction with joint activities to strengthen cooperative relationships between employees in order to reduce employee workload.
- c. It is expected that companies can innovate and create in human resource management to be able to overcome employee work stress.

FURTHER RESEARCH

This research still has limitations so further research needs to be done on this topic "The Effect of Workload and Work Stress on Employee Job Satisfaction on Lucky Plaza Batam Cellular Data Store."

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